

ASSESSING SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE THROUGH ART AND CRAFT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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***Abstract.** The general cultural competence of a person should be understood as a set of knowledge, skills, and elements of cultural experience that allow an individual to freely navigate in a social and cultural environment and operate on its elements. General cultural competencies are a certain range of issues in which the student must be knowledgeable, have knowledge and experience of activity. These are the features of national and universal culture, the cultural foundations of family, social, social phenomena and traditions, the role of science and religion in human life, their impact on the world, competencies in the household and cultural and leisure sphere.*

***Key words.** Developing Early Childhood, Creativity, Craft, Arts.*

Introduction. The general cultural competence of a person should be understood as a set of knowledge, skills, and elements of cultural experience that allow an individual to freely navigate in a social and cultural environment and operate on its elements. General cultural competencies are a certain range of issues in which the student must be knowledgeable, have knowledge and experience of activity. These are the features of national and universal culture, the cultural foundations of family, social, social phenomena and traditions, the role of science and religion in human life, their impact on the world, competencies in the household and cultural and leisure sphere. General cultural competencies are aimed at mastering the methods of physical, spiritual, and intellectual self-development. Self-expression is very important.

Competence includes the following aspects:

- the semantic aspect is an adequate understanding of the situation based on the available cultural patterns of understanding and evaluation of such situations;
- the problem-practical aspect is the adequacy of recognizing the situation, setting and effectively fulfilling goals, tasks, and norms in this situation;
- The communicative aspect is adequate communication, taking into account the relevant cultural patterns of communication and interaction.

A person has general cultural competence if he is capable of adequate understanding, practical solution and communicative expression of situations beyond his professional sphere. In addition, if the problem-practical aspect plays a leading role in professional competence, then the semantic and communicative aspects play a leading role in general cultural competence. The purpose of school education in the field of formation of general cultural competence is: to achieve a level of general cultural competence sufficient for orientation in cultural values, the formation of the ability to independently assess specific cultural phenomena, to master the methods of self-educational activity. The task is to give students the necessary knowledge in the field of culture, to demonstrate samples of culture in various fields, namely: socio-economic; political and legal; in the field of science, religion; environmental; aesthetic; communicative, etc. There are many ways to form a general cultural competence. We are primarily interested in pedagogical ones. Let's focus on some of them. Teachers could use different strategies to make the children attain the skills of making connection with peers and carrying it on, controlling himself, adapting to the environment, carrying out a task in the group, coping with aggressive behaviours, making plans and solving problems. Teachers support children to make them experience speaking skills, respecting others' rights, waiting in the line, solution of a conflict, solving social problems and feeling empathy . For that reason, the teacher must include aesthetic interaction and artistic works in artistic teaching. Aesthetic interactions inform us about complex thinking,

observing, choosing, differentiation, visualizing, hypothesizing, verification, adaptation, perception, and revising, criticizing, reflection, comparing, analysing, synthesizing and evaluating the artistic experiences. These interactions enrich and enlarge intercultural sense. The fact that the artistic works of children become valuable is a result of expressing their thoughts of the views of their friends and teachers over art. Ideas over artistic works make children equipped with necessary sources and skills in order to enrich and express artistic experiences. These studies enlarge the language and communication skills of children, deepen their world views and improve their social skills.

Conclusion. In fine arts lessons dedicated to the study of folk crafts, students also have the opportunity to master such important components of general cultural competence as the ability to evaluate the result of activities and generalize , what is new that has been learned. Thus, the development of folk art crafts in primary classes at the lessons of fine arts can serve as an effective basis for the formation of general cultural competencies among younger schoolchildren. In the pedagogical process of formation of general cultural competencies, there should be no contradictions between competence in the field of modern technology, information technology and in the field of traditional material culture, folk arts and crafts.

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